

**Significant modifications of the administrative structure and procedures to revoke
the EU Fish Export Ban**

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ABSTRACT

During the last 15 years, there has been a phenomenal expansion in the size of the fishing fleet, number of persons employed as fishers, national marine fish production, and total earnings from fish exports. Meanwhile in the global context The European Union was in attempt to combat fishing irregularities of three kinds VIZ: Illegal, Unreported and Unregulated (IUU) fishing. A bans are key instrument the European Commission (EC) uses to tackle IUU fishing. Accordingly on 15th of January 2015, the EC proposed to ban imports of fisheries products from Sri Lanka based on IUU fishing concerns. Since, Sri Lanka was the second largest exporter of fishery products to the EU in 2013, accounted for Euro 74 million of fisheries imports to Europe. Thus the ban had a strong impact to the fisheries industry of Sri Lanka.

As the main implementation agency of fisheries management of Sri Lanka under the Ministry of Fisheries, Department of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources were bounded with a target of implementing a road map with 57 tasks leading to a rapid change in the high seas fisheries operation management process. Significant changes to the regulations concerned, introduction of new management efforts such as Vessel Monitoring system, and fishing trip verification within 24 hours after landing, boat inspections and observer on board were completely new to the administrative system to meet the goal. On the other hand the attitude of the field officers and fishermen on such application was made more challenging.

Administration of DFAR faced the challenge of establishing two new units at head office level; High seas operation unit, Vessel monitoring units and twelve fisheries harbor operation unit with well demarcated work processes incorporating latest technology (i.e. satellite screening) to achieve efficiency level up to EU standards. Co management strategy was adopted to ensure the active participation of fishermen concerned. The national level steering committee established at Prime Minister's office was the best coordinating arm to overcome bottlenecks of the current administrative and financial constrains etc.

The strategic administrative and co management practices adopted based on the SWOT analysis and the ban itself became an opportunity to establish a responsible fisheries culture in Sri Lanka and thus enabled to lift the EU fish export ban on 21st June 2016.

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1.0 Introduction

1.1 The IUU Theory

The international community with a view to ensuring the long-term sustainability of fisheries has established several international fisheries management agreements. Under these agreements a number of conservation and management measures have been adopted including measures to combat illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing (IUU fishing) in high seas. Sri Lanka being a Party to these agreements is bound to implement these conservation and management measures.

In late 90s scientists found that all attempts to manage fisheries was up to the expectations and if the current trend continues each and every commercial fisheries in the world would collapse by year 2050 (Figure 2; The species extinction prediction curve). The reason was identified as weak management decision taken on the basis of fault reporting. The most effective way of managing the fishery was identified as control through consumers, where consumers have to refuse fishery products which are proved to be IUU.

Figure -1; The species extinction prediction curve (Source- Science- The Washington Post)

This successful campaign was strengthened by “The End of the Line: How Overfishing Is Changing the World and What We Eat” is a book published by journalist called Charles Clover and a documentary film called “End of the Line” (Ref: www.endoftheline.com) directed by Rupert Murray. Accordingly most of the consumers (mostly from EU, western countries), pressurized governments and management bodies to apply IUU theories on their

fisheries management plans. Daniel Pauly, a French-born marine biologist, well known for his work in studying human impacts on global fisheries published number of scientific papers supporting the concept.

Meanwhile in 2008 EU issued a Regulation (EC Regulation 1005/2008) requiring all countries of exporting fishery products to EU to implement the conservation and management measures from January 2010 prescribed under the international agreements, particularly imposed by the Indian Ocean Tuna Commission (IOTC) which are highly related to prevent, deter and eliminate the IUU fishing activities.

1.2 Ban on Sri Lankan fish and fishery products by European Union (EU)

Since Sri Lanka has not fulfilled their commitments on prevention of IUU fishing, EU issued a notice of yellow card in 2011. Through its submission dated 14th December 2012, Sri Lanka notified the Commission of the institutional arrangements that have been set up in order to address the issues identified in the suggested Plan of Action. Since then, it has been making several submissions at regular intervals. However, Sri Lanka was unable to fulfill the requirements due to various reasons such as the lack of legal provisions, required manpower and infrastructure facilities, etc. Fisher's attitudes towards responsible fishing were not in a satisfactory level as well. Thus Sri Lanka lagged behind to comply fully with the international standards and left with a compliance rate of only 13% at the end of year 2012 (Figure-2). Accordingly considering the level of non-compliances by November 2014 EU issued the "red card" banning fish imports from Sri Lanka effective from mid-January 2015.

Figure 2: IOTC Compliance score on responsible fisheries of Sri Lanka

EU's view was that there are

about 70+ management deficiencies identified in the high seas fisheries management and catch certificates issuing procedures of Sri Lanka at the point of imposing the fish export ban. The impact of the Red Card is not only defined as a failure of the system but also caused significant income loss to the country during the year 2015 (Figure 3). In presence of huge economic impacts a national responsibility lying with Sri Lanka to overcome these deficiencies in-order to remove the Fish export ban.

Figure 3: Sri Lankan fish export to EU Value in US\$ Dollars millions

2.0 Objectives

1. To identify the strategies and required resources to match the responsibility for implementing the road map
2. To overcome the bottlenecks associated with the state sector administrative structure to complete the work load in term of the road map
3. To coordinate in a successful manner to get active involvement of all stakeholders in completing 57 tasks in terms of the road map
4. Improve communication with EU and perfect timely reporting

3.0 Methodology

3.1 The Road Map

As a result of the initial dialog between Sri Lanka and EU, Road Map which was set up to achieve the required management level. The Road Map consist of 57 Tasks covering main thematic areas of;

- (i) Legal , Regulatory and Enforcement,
- (ii) Training and awareness
- (iii) Capacity building and strengthening operational activities of High seas Fishery Development Unit of DFAR
- (iv) Vessel Monitoring System (VMS) and Fishery Monitoring Centre (FMC) to monitor the fishing boat with satellite facility
- (v) Boat inspection and observer scheme
- (vi) Computerized Data Management System for data reconciliation and electronic data verification are areas assigned to implement on high priority consideration by the Government.

Out of these 57 tasks, 36 have specific timelines while the other 21 fall under the category of “ongoing activities”. It was concluded that 100% of the none-compliances can be achieved by implementing the road map. The utmost activities of the road map however highly technical and active involvement of all stakeholders should be enrolled in order to complete the road map within 08 months of targeted period, that is at the end of November 2015. Accordingly the Department of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources (DFAR) under the Ministry of Fisheries was given with the main responsibility to implement the road map.

3.2 Situation analysis

A SWOT analysis was done in order to determine the exact situation and the potential of DFAR to implement the road map successfully. It was revealed that decision to impose the Red card was mainly taken by EU due to the insufficient progress provided by DFAR on controlling fishermen engaged in IUU fishing and also the catch certificates issued by DFAR to fish exporters are doubting reliability due to lack of transparency and firm systematic fisheries management methodologies. However it was also understood that DFAR had is having inadequate human resources and low level of technology to compatible with the international standards. Therefore it was a great challenge to achieve such a high technical road map with available resources.

Further a detail analysis was conducted in order to identify sufficient information to find the ways to manage available resources and to identify the level of resources needed. Identify the additional budget requirement was also a critical step.

3.3 Co-management strategies

The most important role was to set up a more suitable methodology to get the active involvement of all relevant stakeholders. Small-scale fisheries and the coastal social-ecological systems in which they are embedded with complex systems (Mahon *et al.*, 2008; McClanahan *et al.*, 2008) and Sri Lanka is no exception. Even the multiday fisheries sector in Sri Lanka in spite of its unique characteristics identified as none commercial and small scale sector. Number of studies carried out by various fisheries contents, was confirmed that co-management is the most effective way of managing the small scale and lively hood based fisheries such as the fisheries sector in Sri Lanka (Berkes, 1989; Johannes, 1989). The co-management strategy was therefore identified as the most suitable strategy to achieve the goal. Berkes (1994) framed co-management position within the wider management perspective (Figure 4) proposing several levels of co-management ‘partnership arrangements’, illustrated by the level of power sharing and integration of local and centralized management systems.

Figure 4: A hierarchy of co-management arrangements (adopted from Berkes, 1994).

Based on the above scenario, a number of attempts made to apply co-management in fisheries management of Sri Lanka, through practicing of strategies such as fisheries management areas, fisheries management committees and fisheries society activities. However these steps were not successful due to the high influence of the top down administrative structures. In simple terms, stakeholders' voice came out though the co management arrangement was not highly considered in management decisions.

Therefore in presence of this information, it was decided to adopt a co-management strategy within “joint action”- “advisory role” (Figure 4) level so that government (i.e. DFAR) would get active involvement of all stakeholders as a joint operation while enabling integration of management decision making in a level of “advisory”.

3.4 A customer to be regain

Idea of preventing IUU fishing came out as a pressure from customer with the slogan of “Ask before you buy”. In the context of EU fish export ban, Sri Lanka the supplier who was not able to satisfy the customer (The EU) and fail to convince that products are IUU free.

The actions taken by service providers to respond quickly to service failures could drive positive customer behavior such as re-patronage intention (Smith and Bolton, 2002; Wirtz and Mattila, 2004). Therefore achieving the Road Map and negotiation process was done in a manner focused on regaining the lost trust of the EU by fulfilling all shortcoming pointed out by EU in imposing the Red Card. In other words DFAR had to work towards establishing IUU free responsible fisheries and transparent catch certification procedure even for the grass root level.

3.4 Establishing and motivating the team

It was an accepted fact that technical knowledge of the officers are in a satisfactory level. But to implement the co-management strategy as to the expectation to treat EU as a customer to be regained, the high level of efficiency and good management skills were needful. Motivation and encouragement were essential requirement. In this process the attitudes and the capacity of staff were analyzed. Here even the staff based outside the head office, officers who are at work where high seas fisheries management activities are not taken place were also considered. The age, history of employment, educational back ground and their

achievement at DFAR were also considered. An incentive scheme was introduced in order to motivate the team.

3.5 Awareness

Awareness was the key activity to establish the responsible fisheries culture. There are different kind of programme were conducted apart from field level awareness programme, creative awareness campaign with radio programs targeting fishermen, booklets with simple language to understand the value of having IUU free fisheries, timely scheduled poster campaign was conducted. More than 45 district level seminars for fishermen were conducted and small pocket meeting were also held in Fisheries Inspectors division level. The web site (www.fisheriesdept.gov.lk) was rearranged by introducing a separate section for high seas fisheries information and was regularly updated.

4.0 Results

4.1 Situation analysis

Strengths, weaknesses of DFAR and opportunities and threats available in implementing the Road map were identified through SWOT analysis. An action plan against the road map was prepared in order to use the “strengths” in an effective manner, to overcome the weakness. Potential threats were handled by using the opportunities available. The action plan consisted of all processors with the clearly defined responsibilities of the team.

Mentioning below is the results of SWOT analysis

<u>Strengths</u> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Admin structure/ man power2. Legal provision to implement the road map is already available with fisheries act3. Procurement of Vessel monitoring system was almost complete4. Government support and political will to implement the road map was positive5. Funding availability	<u>Weaknesses</u> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Current staff is not fully committed2. Lack of awareness3. Lack of technical knowledge4. Lack of coordination
<u>Opportunities</u> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. To reform the fisheries law2. To restructure DFAR staff3. To use IT and latest technology	<u>Threats</u> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Attitudes of fishermen2. Trade issues3. Admin issues

Figure 5; Results of SWOT analysis conducted in order to determine the exact situation and to identify the potentials of DFAR to complete the road map

4.2 Co-management arrangements

A national level steering committee was adopted and the committee meetings were scheduled bi-weekly. The committee was consist of the national level representatives of relevant stakeholders. Progress of the road map has to be reported by the committee to the economic affairs progress meeting chaired by Hon. Prime Minister. Table 1 indicates the details of members of the steering committee and nature of their responsibilities. Figure 6 indicates the coordination arrangements in different level to implement the road map successfully.

Apart from these members, representative from other relevant organizations as required time to time was called for the meetings in order to clear the bottle necks and also to get the technical support (i.e., Ministry of Defense, Ports Authority, University of Colombo, Telecom, NARA). Advisors of the Prime minister were also participated in order to get the political support to implement the Road Map. Representatives of EU embassy of Sri Lanka were also participated in order to provide their ideas on improving the process. A key coordinator was appointed by the Embassy of Sri Lanka of Brussels to work closely with DFAR on reporting purposes and this was a positive move because it assisted to overcome the gaps and shortcomings created between the EU and Sri Lanka during the reporting.

Table 1; Membership of Steering committee to implement the Road Map to revoke Fish Export ban and their responsibilities

No	Member	Responsibility in brief
01	Sectary of Prime Minister	Coordinate the committee and report the progress. Overall supervision
02	Sectary of Ministry of Fisheries	Overall supervision
03	DFAR	Main implementation and reporting body of the Road Map and Enforcement of the newly introduced fisheries law
04	NAVY and Coast Guard	Enforcement of the newly introduced fisheries law
05	Harbor corporation	Fisheries harbor management and support port state measures
06	Foreign Ministry	Coordination with EU embassy and embassy of Sri Lanka in Brussels, EU
07	Attorney Generals Department and Legal Draftsman's Department	Introduction of new fisheries regulations and amendment of fisheries act when necessary
08	National Treasury/ budget department	Provide the budgetary requirements and support on financial procedures
09	Department of commerce	Technical support on economic applications
10	Telecommunication regulatory commission	Technical support on radio call sings for fishing boats
11	VMS service provider (local representative)	To complete installment of VMS and establishment of VMS center
12	Representatives of fish exporters	Technical support and provide recommendation on fish export procedures
13	Representatives of fishermen who supply fish for export	Technical support and provide recommendation on implementing the fisheries management activities

Committee was also arranged in each district to identify the bottlenecks and to provide recommendations to the national level committee. Fisheries Assistant Director of the district coordinated the proceedings of the committee. Officers were appointed from the head office level in order to coordinate with above members of the district committee so that the communication gaps were filled effectively.

Figure 6; Co-management arrangements to implement the Road map to revoke EU fish export ban.

4.3 Establishing the team and motivating them to achieve the peak

A team called High Seas Management Unit (HSFU) was appointed. Out of DFAR employees especially who worked for the private sector previously was selected to the unit. It was believed that people who had the experience in private sector would understand the gravity of “Customer to be regained theory” and will be able to adapt for working conditions with co-management arrangements.

A cabinet paper was submitted on appointing the team with all responsibilities were clearly documented (Figure 7). An intensive of 50% of the salary during the Road Map implementing period was also approved by the cabinet. Separate Assistant Director (Staff

Level) was appointed to implement the VMS and another Assistant Director, who is qualified with CIM, UK and worked as a Business Development Manager in the private sector was appointed to overlook the HSFU. A staff level officer was appointed to implement the operational procedures and to coordinate the grassroots level. In order to expedite the process, even tiny corner is touched. Since it was identified that preparation of letters taking more time pre-formatted letters were introduced. No separate envelopes were used letter itself become an envelope when folded. An IT system called ResFish was introduced in order to run the daily duties in an effective way. Everyone was tasked to provide weekly progress of their duties.

Figure 7: The Implementation Process of the High Seas Management Process

An office of DFAR was established in 12 fisheries harbors (Figure 8) where high seas fisheries activities were taking place to manage and implement newly introduced management measures such as;

- Boat departures and arrival procedures
- Boat inspections
- Duties related to Log book and active log operation
- Observer deputation
- Legal enforcements at harbours

Officers in this office operating in all 07 days for 24 hours basis (24/7). The container boxes converted with all facilities were used as the offices in most harbours since there is no time or space to establish the buildings. 80 new officers were recruited to support the existing staff of these harbor and later on a risk allowance of Rs.5000.00 was provided them as well. These harbor officers Additionally watch huts and officers provided at the harbor mouth for NAVY and coast guard to actively monitor the boat departures and arrivals on 24/7 basis. Altogether the DFAR staff engaged directly in the Road Map was about 147. More than 4000 fishermen and staff of about 34 fish exporting establishment were engaged in the process directly.

Figure 8; Harburs offices network of DFAR (Established in year 2015)

4.4 Progress of the road map

After 08 months of continuous processing of the road map was successfully implemented for the said period of 08 months. Unlike before 2014, the implementation at the grassroots level is visible. The fishermen who had demonstrations against VMS on early 2014, was actively involved in the High seas management activities at harbours. A Team from EU

visited Sri Lanka in November 2015 to review the progress against the road map. Some more suggestions was provided by EU in order to maintain the achieved success in a long run and those were also to be implemented by April 2016. It was mentioned that the evaluation was successful and after a long technical dialogue a positive report from DGMARE (Directorial General of Maritime Affairs) of EU submitted a positive report on April 2016. Accordingly the Ban was lifted on June 2016.

Indicated in the Table 2 is the comparison of the current situation and the situation in 2014 when the Ban was imposed.

Table 2: Comparison between the “Current Situation” and the situation “When Ban Imposed related to the high seas fisheries management processes

Aspect	Situation in year 2014 (when the Fish Ban is imposed)	Situation in year 2016 (when the Fish Ban is lifted)
Legal and international requirements on board	Less no of boats complied with legal and international standards	All high seas boats with legal and international standards 1. Active VMS 2. International call sign 3. Proper gear markings 4. legal fishing gears 5. Logbooks 6. All other requirements mentioned in the High seas operation regulation
Legal Framework	Fines limited to Rs.2000 to 25,000	Fines imposed from Rs. Mn. 1.0 to Rs. Mn 150
	Administrative fines not practiced	Administrative fines fully in place
	No regulations to manage high seas fishing operations	07 New regulations introduced Act amended for 03 times
	No operational procedures	Comprehensive operational manuals available
	No annual plans	05 annual plans introduced
	Basic NPOA-IUU	Updated NPOA-IUU
Vessel Monitoring System (VMS)	No FMC	FMC with full operation
	No VMS fitted Boats	All High Seas Boats fitted with VMS

	No verification of trips	100% verification of trips
	Less actions against violations at high sea	Actions will be taken 100%
	Minimum amount of details about the boats after departs	Boat owners knows the exact details of the location of their trips
	No dedicated rescues boats in place	Two dedicated rescues boats in place
Log book data	Less numbers of log book on board	100% of the boats are with log books
	No log sheet certification	100% log sheet certification
	Less departure inspection	100% departure inspection
	Less boat inspection	Covered more than 25% of landings (> 10%)
	No catch certificates issued based on verifications and log sheet details	catch certificates issued 100% based on verifications and log sheet details
	No e-log book	Sri Lankan made e-log book System (collaboration with University of Colombo-School of Computing) is available
Observer Scheme	Less Observer deputation	100% Observer deputation (for 24m+)
	No solution for the observers below 24m vessels	Alternative observer scheme covered 5% of the landings
Port State Measures	No Regulation and the management frame work	Regulation and the management frame work established
	Lack of officers trained	Officers trained and already practicing PSM for maintenances

IOTC Reporting	No comprehensive data base for log sheet data	Available
	No on-time reports to IOTC	100% on time reports to IOTC
	No Catch data on length frequency	Available
	No Gird wise catch and effort data	Available
	Compliance rate (42%)	Expected to record more that 75%
Human Resources and Financial Support	No harbor offices	12 new harbor offices established
	No High Seas Fisheries Unit (HSFU)	HSFU with 147 officers associated with it
	No facilities	Each and every offices fully equipped
	Less no of dedicated officers	147 dedicated officers
	Less coordination	Web based coordination
	No incentives	Incentive worth of 23% of the salary
	Low allocations	High amounts (more then Rs. Mn. 200 annually)
	No officer insurance	Insurance scheme of Rs. Mn. 2.5
Training and awareness	Low level of Training	High level of Training
	Low level of awareness	High level of awareness
	No compendium for fisheries act	Available and updated
	No displays at harbours	all details including blacklisted fishermen and boats displayed at harbours
	No guidelines	Comprehensive guideline for high seas fisheries management
	No booklets	Available

	No targeted posters	Available
	No video promotions	Available
Coordination among stakeholders	No regular NPOA-IUU meeting	Regular NPOA-IUU meeting (at least in 03 months intervals)
	Stakeholder involvement for the decision making	All decisions related to combat against IUU are being made at NPOA-IUU meeting including the revision of the Fisheries Act, Regulations, Annual plans,...etc
	No high level steering committee	Available and monthly meetings going on
	No district coordination committees	Available and monthly meetings going on
	No electronic system for proper coordination	Web based interface development in place
Staff and Service	No 24/7 service	24/7 service
	Discouraged staff	Encouraged staff
	Low attitudes fishermen	fishermen with high attitudes
	Lack of Ppolicies	Positive Policies
	Lack of management mechanism	Mechanism 100% activated
	Far from the Rresponsible fisheries culture	All the way ttowards a Responsible fisheries culture

5.0 Discussion

It was a strong opinion among public that the rapid management process cannot be successfully implemented in the state sector due to the influences of various procedures and rules. It is vital to understand that rules and procedures are put in place because of those are to enable firm decision making process. In addition the responsibility of positive or negative impact of a decision taken is shared and facilitate, because of an absence of an individual personal who can act as an owner of such government organization. Therefore way of thinking to make decision should be in accordance with a pre-defined scenario. In this connection, it is important to realize this scenario as an opportunity to overcome weakness rather than trying to change the whole system.

However the situation concerned if it is correctly analyzed and if the officers are provided with clearly defined responsibilities with better rewards, any kind of deadline can be achieved even in the state sector. It is important to avoid the coordination noises and to listen to the grassroot level users during the implementation. Adopting co-management in a creative manner will result “good” not only in a community management but for any situation where active involvement of both public and private sector is needed. Thus implementation of the road map to revoke fish export ban of EU can be considered as a good lesson learnt for adopting co-management in a successful manner.

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